

Renal Cell Carcinoma Invading the Descending Colon

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Introduction:-

Renal cell carcinoma makes for 3% of adult cancers, and 25% of cases show signs of local invasion or metastasis to nearby structures. Colon involvement, which affects 1% of RCC cases, is uncommon. There have only been seven of these cases documented to date, and six of those cases have histologically shown sarcomatoid differentiation, which is consistent with locally aggressive behavior. The patient in this case has descending colon direct invasion by left-sided renal cell carcinoma, which has been histologically shown to exhibit sarcomatoid differentiation.

Case Description: A 59-year-old man arrived with constipation and painless postpartum hemorrhage in the month before, along with left-sided loin pain that had persisted for three months. For two months, he complained of partial bowel evacuation and appetite loss. Haematuria or fever bouts did not occur. There were no comorbidities in him. Before receiving a diagnosis, he smoked one to two cigarettes a day. His family had no history of renal or any other type of cancer. The patient did not appear pale upon examination. An examination of

the abdomen revealed no masses, but there was some minor left-sided loin pain. There was no left-sided varicocele found.

Regarding private medical treatment. A mixed echogenic mass in the left kidney, favoring a renal tumor, was seen on an abdominal USS. A left-sided renal cell carcinoma in the lower pole measuring 9.7×7.7×6.5 cm that infiltrated into the proximal descending colon was confirmed by a CECT of the patient's abdomen performed in the ward. A left nephrectomy with a probable left hemicolectomy was planned, and agreement was obtained for a potential stoma to be taken. A preoperative Hb of 8.3g/dl was found, and the patient had blood transfusions to improve.

The tumor mass was discovered during the procedure to have grown across the left kidney's lower pole, penetrated the descending colon, and then adhered to the anterior abdominal wall. The tumor spread to the quadratus lumborum muscle posteriorly. A superior connection was present with the left hemidiaphragm. Access to the primary tumor was obtained through segmental excision of the distal transverse and descending colon that was involved. The bowel's lumen was totally blocked by the tumor. A portion of the renal bed, upper descending colon, and transverse colon were removed, together with the left kidney with tumor, all in one piece. In order to avoid a colostomy, primary anastomosis of the transverse and descending colons was performed. The patient's initial post-operative care required an ICU admission. The patient was discharged on day 9.

Histology:-

The tumor measured 6 x 7 x 8 and included the whole thickness of the colon. Renal arteries and the ureter were unaffected, and the resection margins were clearly defined. Under a microscope, sarcomatoid regions with potential rhabdoid differentiation were seen in the majority of the tumor, while clear cell renal carcinoma was visible in portion of the tumor. The invasive tumor's infiltrative component exhibited a mostly sarcomatoid alteration. It was determined that the patient had Stage 4 Clear Cell Renal Carcinoma with Sarcoid/Rhabdoid Differentiation (pT4,pN0 Mx).

Follow up:-

Patient was clinically well on his follow up appointment. Referral to oncological services was arranged with histology reports.

Discussion:

Renal cell carcinoma ranks seventh globally in terms of frequency of malignancy, representing 2.2% of all cancer cases each year. It spreads by distant metastasis or local invasion. 2% of tumors are locally invasive; these types are more aggressive and have a poorer prognosis. They typically affect the

ipsilateral adrenal gland, the renal vein, the IVC, the retroperitoneal lymph nodes, and in rare cases, nearby organs. Because the liver, spleen, pancreas, colon, and duodenum are intraperitoneally located and the tumor is adequately encapsulated, these organs are typically spared. When GI tract involvement occurs in RCC, it usually results from distant metastases and is extremely rare. The traditional trio of loin mass, flank pain, and haematuria only manifests in 10% of patients. RCCs are discovered by accident in 60% of cases. The gold standard for diagnosis is CECT Abdomen, which evaluates the size of the tumor, its involvement of other organs, the infiltration of local lymph nodes, and the condition of the kidney on the other side.

Only 7 previous published cases of colon invading RCC have been recorded, highlighting the rarity of extensive bowel invasion. Their anatomical separation from one another is the cause of this.

Sarcomatoid differentiation is the most prevalent type of tumor dedifferentiation and can occur in any kind of RCC. They are advanced (stage 3 or 4) at diagnosis, with over 50% presenting with distant metastases or locally occurring metastases. The prognosis worsens with increasing proportion of sarcomatoid alteration; 5-year survival rates for sarcomatoid RCCs are 22%, whereas non-sarcomatoid RCCs are 79%. Because RCC is infamously resistant to chemotherapy, surgery has been the cornerstone of treatment for the condition. Immunomodulators, radiation, and radiofrequency ablation have all shown results.

The best practical course of action for patients with colon invasion is still a radical nephrectomy combined with radical en bloc resection, with the goal of obtaining negative resection margins. Since these circumstances are uncommon, there are no precise rules for making decisions. Open radical surgery is warranted, nonetheless, if the patient is healthy and stable. In summary, the choice to operate on this patient resulted in a lower disease burden and avoided the potentially disastrous GI hemorrhage, intestinal blockage, or perforation that some of the other documented instances showed. Sarcoid differentiation indicates that RCC affecting the colon is invariably aggressive. The presentation is still unique.

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